

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to stem rot (SR) and bacterial blight (BB)

H. Chand, R. Singh, and D. V. S. Panwar, Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station (HAURRS), Kaul, Haryana, India

SR, caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, and BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, are major rice diseases in Haryana. We evaluated 177 early- to mid-duration rices for their reaction to those diseases at HAURRS in 1983-84.

Each entry was planted in 2-m rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip inoculated with a BB suspension at maximum tillering and scored for resistance using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. SR screening was in field plots and also in the laboratory. In the laboratory, cut stem pieces were wound-inoculated with a small piece of agar-cultured *S. oryzae*. The inoculated stems were kept in standing position with a test tube rack in a tray with 2.5 cm of water. They were covered with plastic bags to retain high moisture and incubated at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 10 d after inoculation. Entries with lesions less than 10 mm long were

Rices with SR and BB resistance, Haryana, India.

Entry	Parentage	Reaction ^a to		
		SR		BB
		Field	Laboratory	
HAU118-87	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
HAU118-110	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
HAU118-111	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
BR51-282-8	IR20/IR5-114-3-1	R	R	R
IR42	IR1561-228//4*IR24/O. nivara///CR 94-13	R	R	R
IR2588-34-5-6	IR1544-238-2-3/IR1529-680-3	R	R	R
IR2681-90-4	CR94///IR20 ³ /O. nivara//IR1541-102-6	R	R	MR
HAU118-163	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-195	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-752	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-754	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-755	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
IR54	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88// IR2061-214-3-6-20	MR	MR	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

considered resistant; those with 10-30 mm lesions, moderately resistant; and those with more than 30 mm, susceptible.

Disease pressure was high for SR (location severity index [LSI] 6.79 in the field and 6.05 in the laboratory), and

moderate (LSI 3.12) for BB. Of the entries tested, 125 showed resistance to BB, 19 to field SR, and 44 to laboratory SR. Six entries were resistant to both BB and SR (see table) and had good agronomic traits. □

Evaluation of hill rice germplasm for leaf blast (BI) resistance

J. C. Bhatt and V. S. Chauhan, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture (VLHA), Almora 263601 India

BI is a serious constraint to rice production in hilly regions. We evaluated 1,271 cultivars from the hill area of Uttar Pradesh for BI resistance under artificial epiphytic conditions at the VLHA experimental farm at Hawalbagh (1,250 mean sea level).

Cultivars were planted in the Uniform Blast Nursery pattern. VL8 was the resistant check and Ch 1039 and HR12 were the susceptible checks. Although the initial inoculum was sufficient to start

Reaction of 1,271 cultivars to B1 at 30, 40, and 57 DAS, Almora, India.

SES score	30 DAS		40 DAS		57 DAS	
	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)
0	20	1.6	1	0.1	0	0
1	33	2.6	0	0.0	0	0
2	101	7.9	8	0.6	0	0
3	430	41.7	27	2.1	0	0
4	587	46.2	633	49.8	17	1.3
5	0	—	573	45.1	132	10.4
6	0	—	28	2.2	309	24.3
7	0	—	1	0.1	583	45.9
8	0	—	0	—	184	14.5
9	0	—	0	—	46	3.6

infection, for heavy disease pressure we prepared a fresh conidial suspension from infected leaves and sprayed it on 15-d-old

seedlings. The nursery was planted on 3 Jul 1982 and BI incidence was recorded 30, 40, and 57 d after sowing (DAS). In

Aug, when disease incidence was recorded, weather favored B1. Average weekly maximum and minimum temperatures were 28.1 and 18.6°C and average relative humidity was 78%. There were 21 rainy days during the month, and intermittent drizzle and cloud cover encouraged disease development. B1 incidence was rated using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice

(SES) 0-9 scale (see table).

At 30 d, 53.79% of the cultivars were resistant; at 40 d only 2.81% were resistant. At 57 d only the resistant check VL8 scored resistant. However, 17 cultivars had some resistance and displayed slow blasting. They were VHC85, VHC218, VHC976, VHC1080, VHC1098, VHC1296, VHC1404, VHC1487,

VHC1488, VHC1493, VHC1494, VHC1508, VHC1583, VHC1759, VHC1760, VHC1761, and VHC1824. These have potential as commercial varieties and for breeding programs to incorporate B1 resistance into improved varieties. □

Negative selection in breeding for quantitative resistance to rice blast (BI) under upland nursery conditions

S. W. Ahn, E. Tulande, and M. Rubiano, Rice Program, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia

In 1983 we evaluated 149 F₄ rice lines for reaction to B1 under upland nursery conditions in Colombia. The entries were derived from crosses between CICA4 (low resistance), IR11-452-1-1 (intermediate resistance), and Tapuripa and Camponi (high resistance). Evaluations were made using the relative evaluation system for B1 and by measuring panicle B1 severity based on disease incidence and intensity.

In the nursery, 70% of the lines with low quantitative B1 resistance in earlier generations had the same reaction in F₅ (see table). However, the reactions of more than 60% of the lines with high or intermediate resistance and the no-infection type differed from those in previous generations.

Field evaluation of a limited number of lines showed that more than 60% of

the intermediate-resistance and no-infection types reacted differently from the previous generations; however, more than 65% of those with high and low resistance gave the same reaction.

A highly susceptible reaction is a reliable indication that a low level of quantitative resistance, compatible races, and a favorable microclimate were all present. But reactions of high and intermediate quantitative resistance, or no-infection type plants alone cannot exclude possible cryptic errors, such as lack of compatible races, insufficient inoculum, or unfavora-

ble microclimate during disease development, particularly in the field.

The results strongly suggest that to attain higher levels of quantitative resistance, which presumably will be more stable, vigorous negative selection made throughout all generations is preferable to positive selection — selection only for plants with less disease. Proper plot design and management are also important to provide a favorable disease environment. Use of diversified inoculum will reduce the masking effect of qualitative resistance on quantitative resistance. □

Change of quantitative resistance to rice blast, Colombia.^a

Resistance in F ₂ , F ₃ , and F ₄	Frequency (%) in F ₅									
	Nursery ^b					Field ^c				
	Total no.	N	N	I	L	Total no.	N	H	I	L
H	28	46	32	18	4	6	17	66	0	17
I	38	10	<u>21</u>	37	32	9	0	<u>22</u>	33	44
L	49	6	8	<u>16</u>	70	19	0	0	<u>5</u>	95
N	34	<u>32</u>	9	26	<u>33</u>	12	<u>33</u>	33	17	<u>17</u>

^a H = high, I = intermediate, L = low, N = no infection. Underlined values indicate % of lines that exhibit the same reaction as in previous generations. ^b Blast nursery at CIAT, Palmira, Colombia. ^c Santa Rosa Station, Villavicencio, Colombia.

Inheritance of moderate resistance to blast (BI) in rice

H. S. Suh, College of Agriculture and Animal Science, Yeungnam University, Gyeongsan, 632, Korea; F. L. Nuque and J. M. Bonman, Plant Pathology Department; and G. S. Khush, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

We crossed the upland rice cultivars Dourado Precose from Brazil and OS6 from Nigeria, both with moderate resistance to B1 race IH-1 (isolate 43), with susceptible Tongil and highly

resistant Milyang 54. The F₂ plants of the crosses and their parents were screened with the race IH-1. B1 reaction was scored 0 to 9 using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

The reaction of the F₂ seedlings of the crosses Tongil/Dourado Precose and Tongil/OS6 are shown in Figure 1. The score of Dourado Precose was 1-3; that of OS6 was 0 to 4; and that of Tongil was 4 to 9. Both F₂ populations had reaction scores from 0 to 9, with an almost bimodal distribution. Those results indicated that their moderate B1 resistance is monogenic.

If we divide the F₂ segregants into two groups (resistant-moderately resistant and susceptible), based on the infection range of the parents, the segregation pattern is 3:1. However, the peaks of the distribution curves for the resistant and moderately resistant groups did not fit the average of the moderately resistant parents.

When the F₂ populations of the crosses of Dourado Precose or OS6 and Milyang 54 were screened with the same race, the distribution curves were also abnormal (Fig. 2). Milyang 54 scored 0, but the score of Dourado Precose or OS6